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DEEP SUBMERGENCE DESIGN OF INTERSECTING COMPOSITE SPHERES

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ABSTRACT

This report contains the design philosophy and development of a 1.2 meter diameter, composite, spherical pressure hull. The design incorporates a thermoset graphite/epoxy (AS4/309) to 6AL-4V ELI titanium trapped reinforcement joint. Numerous design iterations were made to achieve a balanced design which satisfied the collapse pressure. 3-D nonlinear finite element analyses with gap and interface elements were made using the ABAQUS [1] code. The final design achieved a weight savings of 46% of the equivalent steel sphere, and satisfied the through thickness allowable strain limit of -0.004200 mm/mm or an average stress of -283 MPa at design collapse pressure. Localized bending strains in the vicinity of the titanium joint were $-.005750$ mm/mm or a localized stress of -386 MPa. The fabrication of the sphere will use the fiber placement method to achieve a quasi-isotropic layup and an out-of-autoclave cure.

KEYWORDS: Thermoset Composites; Composites to Metal Joints; Spherical Shells; In-Situ Cure; Finite Element Analysis

1.0 INTRODUCTION

One of the objectives of the designer of deep submersibles is to minimize the weight of the pressure hull. The hull with the lowest weight to buoyancy ratio for a given depth is advantageous since the remaining weight can be applied to increased payload, propulsion or life support. These improvements can be achieved through advanced hull concepts and/or efficient material systems, such as advanced composites. The intersecting spheres concept combines the functional advantages of the cylinder and the weight advantages of the sphere for deep submergence and was chosen as the candidate pressure hull configuration. Advanced composites introduces a highly efficient material system with a high strength/high stiffness to weight ratio. Considerable experience and knowledge exists regarding the performance, joining, and

damage tolerance of these composite materials for thin aerospace applications where the high tensile strength of the composite is fully utilized. However a database of experience and knowledge on the use of advanced composites for thick cylindrical or spherical applications in compression for deep submergence does not exist.

This paper discusses the design of a composite bispherical pressure hull model incorporating a graphite thermoset sphere joined to a graphite thermoset sphere by means of titanium reinforcing ring. This paper, also, addresses the determination of: allowable strength and stiffness properties; mechanically trapped joining methods for accessibility; considerations for the effects of imperfections; failure criteria selection; and process producibility considerations. While autoclave filament wound thermoset spheres may be practical for scale models, full scale articles will require a fiber placement out-of-autoclave cure with in process inspection to be affordable. As such, the joining method, layup, strength properties, quality assurance, and choice of fiber strongly influenced the design. The final design thus reflected a concurrent engineering approach. This work was funded by DARPA [2].

2.0 PRELIMINARY DESIGN

The controlling dimensions of the selected spherical and bispherical models were a 1.2 meter inside diameter of the sphere and a minimum 40.64 cm clear bore diameter at the reinforcing ring, as shown in Figure 1. Candidate materials were AS4/3501-6, S-Glass/Epoxy or AS4/309 graphite/epoxy. The reinforcing ring used to join the composite spheres was selected as 6Al-4V ELI titanium to provide better stiffness compatibility, corrosion resistance, and lower weight than steel.

2.1 Intersecting Composite Sphere Design Philosophy The criterion utilized in the preliminary sizing of the intersecting ring is based on matching the shell displacements with the ring displacements so as to avoid inducing large bending stresses in the shell. The ring material may be either integral with the sphere material (i.e. the same) or of composite material construction (i.e. different materials). All material is assumed to be quasi-isotropic. For our case, the radial deflection in the ring (Figure 1), based on Lamé's solution [3] for two intersecting spheres of equal thickness, is given by:

$$\delta_2 = \frac{pR^2 \sin\alpha \cos\alpha}{bE_r} \left(\frac{r_2^2 + r_1^2}{r_2^2 - r_1^2} - \nu_r \right) \quad (1)$$

The corresponding deflection of the sphere is:

$$\delta_2 = \frac{p \sin \alpha R^2}{2hE_s} (1 - \nu_s) \quad (2)$$

Assuming a sphere thickness and material and ring material, the corresponding ring size can be computed.

2.2 Selection of Spherical Buckling Parameters

The classical axisymmetric elastic buckling pressure for an ideal spherical shell is calculated by [4]:

$$P_{cr} = \frac{2E_s}{\sqrt{3(1 - \nu_s^2)}} \left(\frac{t_s}{R_1} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

However, experience with fabricated metal spheres has shown that due to: adverse boundary conditions, initial deviations from sphericity, and other departures from the ideal, a reduction in buckling strength is appropriate. Based upon axisymmetric bifurcation test data on steel heads [5], the reduction recommended is 0.7. Thus,

$$P'_{cr} = \frac{1.4E_s}{\sqrt{3(1 - \nu_s^2)}} \left(\frac{t_s}{R_1} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

The effects of residual stresses and out-of-roundness leads to further reduction in collapse pressure of:

$$P_{exp} = kP'_{cr} \quad (5)$$

For metal spheres, the critical buckling pressure above the proportional limit with fabrication effects is expressed in terms of local geometry as:

$$P''_E = kP'_E = k \frac{1.4\sqrt{E_{sec}E_t}}{\sqrt{3(1 - \nu_s^2)}} \left(\frac{t_s}{R_{10}} \right)^2 \quad (6)$$

The k factors that represent the lowest envelopes of test results on fabricated spherical models are chosen according to the method of fabrication, the material and the margin of stability of the shell. When buckling controls above the proportional limit, the collapse pressure is determined by calculating the average stress in the sphere as:

$$\sigma_{avg} = \frac{P(R_{10})^2}{2t_s R_1} \quad (7)$$

For ideally perfectly plastic materials, the inelastic pressure is given by:

$$P_y = \frac{2t_s R_1}{(R_{10})^2} \sigma_y \quad (8)$$

For the stability, the local radius of curvature, R_1 , was assumed to be 10% greater than the normal radius, R , of the hull. The deviation from sphericity measured over a critical arc length, L_c , can be determined from empirical data developed at DTRC [5] and for our case the relationship can be expressed by:

$$R_1/R = 1.38 (\Delta/t_s) + 1.0 \quad \text{or} \quad \Delta/t_s = 0.072464 \quad (9)$$

The k factor assumed for the preliminary design was based on test results on 1.68 meter diameter steel hemispheres to be 0.76 which corresponds to a design collapse pressure of:

$$P''_{cr} = 0.76P'_{cr} = \frac{1.06E_s}{\sqrt{3(1-\nu_s^2)}} \left(\frac{t_s}{R_1} \right)^2 \quad (10)$$

which, rounding off, gives:

$$t_s^2 = \frac{\sqrt{3(1-\nu_s^2)} (P''_{cr} R_1^2)}{E_s} \quad (11)$$

This design procedure had been proven successful in earlier designs of boron/glass-epoxy and titanium intersecting spheres [6]. Based upon equation 11, a preliminary sphere thickness of 1.91 cm was calculated using average properties for graphite/epoxy and then the titanium reinforcing ring dimensions were determined.

2.3 Initial Titanium Reinforcing Ring Size

The preliminary design details of the 1.2 meter diameter composite sphere and titanium joint is shown in Figure 2. Once this size was determined, the preliminary mechanically trapped joint and 1.91 cm thick composite sphere with a quasi-isotropic layup were evaluated. A number of different composite materials were employed in BOSOR4 [7] axisymmetric shell analyses to determine the relative strength of each. The CMAP [8] composite materials analysis program was utilized to calculate the effective material properties and to perform the ply by ply failure analyses, from the BOSOR4 program force resultants. Table 1 summarizes the results of some of these evaluations. These simplified analyses provided a general guide as to the relative performance of the various carbon-fiber composites, but more realistic finite element analyses were required to better determine the true state of strain and to model the mechanical joint.

2.4 Allowables The material allowables for the design of the 1.2 meter diameter sphere progressed considerably as the design evolved to fabrication. The initial sizing of the sphere considered published ultimate stress and strain data for AS4/3501-6 and S-Glass/Epoxy. The initial thickness was selected based on average material properties to satisfy buckling using preliminary knockdown factors for the assumed fabrication methods with AS4/3501-6 as the baseline material. The maximum compressive strain allowable was initially selected as $-.006250$ mm/mm, which was about 65% of the ultimate lamina compressive strain and in agreement with recorded failure test on unstiffened composite cylinders [9]. However, as a result of discussions with fabricators and contractors in the program, the revised procedure outlined below in Section 2.4.1 was developed.

2.4.1 Lamina and Laminate Ultimate Design Allowables B-Basis values were obtained by multiplying the RT Dry values by $.80$ to $.85$ as suggested by MIL-HANDBOOK-17B in lieu of actual B-Basis values for AS4/3501-6. Ultimate Allowable Values were originally obtained by multiplying the B-Basis values by a further knockdown to account for wet property effects, fabrication variations and thickness. This resulted in an initial maximum compressive strain allowable of $-.005600$ and $-.010250$ mm/mm for AS4/3501-6 and AS4/309, respectively. Eventhough the preceding allowable values were considered reasonable for mature design, it was felt that stronger consideration should be given to the effects of curvature, fiber waviness, wet properties, effects of decreased fiber volume, possible increased porosity and notch sensitivity. Since the weight reduction objectives were assured and to insure success, additional knockdowns were applied for each of these factors to determine the final laminate maximum compressive allowables for AS4/3501-6 and AS4/309 as $-.004200$ mm/mm in both cases.

3.0 DETAILED DESIGN

The first detailed axisymmetric finite element sphere joint model is shown in Figure 3. This model was a 180° - 8 noded axisymmetric solid finite element model with 170 elements in the composite shell, 15 element for the inner titanium ring and 28 elements for the outer titanium ring. The analysis was performed using the finite element analysis program FESOL [10] with axisymmetric solid elements with the quasi-isotropic material properties for AS4/3501.6, shown in Table 2. The analysis assumed a symmetric boundary

condition on the vertical face of the outer titanium ring to simulate the condition represented by intersecting spheres. The interface between the composite and the titanium rings was assumed to behave as if perfectly bonded. To better assess the transversely quasi-isotropic behavior of the sphere, the ABAQUS program was then selected because of its proven reliability, ability to accurately account for fully orthotropic material properties, and the ability to model interfaces and gaps. The typical results of these analyses shown in Table 3, indicate that the through thickness stiffness has a significant effect on the meridional strain. Prior to ABAQUS analysis, when isotropic material properties were used, the peak strains were below allowable values, but with the introduction of 3D properties the initial maximum compressive strain allowable was now exceeded. The problem was the high meridional strain near the end of the titanium ring on the inner surface. This high strain was a result of the crimping of the sphere in this region as shown in the Figure 4. This crimping was due to the large difference in stiffness between the sphere and ring. A number of iterations with reduced ring dimensions lowered the peak strain to -0.00635 mm/mm. In all of these models the hoop and radial strain changes are insignificant or unimportant. All of these reductions in the titanium ring size resulted in a significant decrease in the kinking of the sphere and the corresponding maximum compressive strain. However, the peak strain was still higher than the initial maximum allowable strain. A simplified analysis demonstrated that a bonded composite to titanium joint would fail, and suggested the possibility of a bolted joint. A bolted joint through the pressure boundary was, however, considered unacceptable due to additional knockdowns and concerns for leakage and bearing failure at the holes. It was felt that the mechanically trapped joint would be acceptable, provided adequate clamping action existed. The adequacy of the clamping force was determined via a nonlinear contact analysis. The model was analyzed with gap and interface elements using ABAQUS to simulate the interfaces between the composite and titanium ring and the two titanium ring pieces. The peak compressive strain was reduced to -0.00484 mm/mm, which was acceptable for the initial allowables, with a maximum separation or gap of 0.21 mm indicating that there was adequate clamping action. After a few more iterations with different thicknesses and ring sizes, a 1.651 cm thick AS4/3501-6 sphere was found to be adequate (Table 3).

3.1 Model With AS4/309 Properties

Up to this point the sizing of the composite sphere and titanium joint was done with AS4/3501-6 properties and

initial allowables. However, the first sphere will be made with AS4/309 and the laminate properties of Table 2. The 1.651 cm thick model results with AS4/309 properties are shown in Table 3. As can be seen maximum meridional strain is -0.00644 mm/mm. These strains fall below the initial allowables, however because of the concerns noted in earlier the sphere and joint was redesigned to accommodate a more conservative compressive strain allowable.

3.2 Redesign of Sphere and Joint Due to a Change in Allowables

Using a maximum compressive strain allowable of -0.004200 mm/mm away from the joint for both AS4/3501-6 and AS4/309 to insure success, the 1.651 cm sphere was no longer adequate, and a thicker sphere was required. The final design was a constant thickness 1.85 cm sphere of AS4/309 with a 1.27 mm build-up in the joint region (Figure 5). The strains are presented in Table 3. The maximum meridional strain away from the joints was -0.004310 mm/mm and a localized -0.005750 mm/mm at the end of the composite (Figure 6). The build-up could be replaced by fiberglass to better transfer the high strain. The computed weight of the 1.85 cm thick 1.2 meter sphere was 134 kilograms. This computes to a 46% weight savings with the composite shell when compared to an equivalent steel sphere.

4.0 CONCLUSIONS

Numerous design iterations were made to achieve a balanced design, which satisfied the design collapse pressure loading. The final design of the thermoset sphere with AS4/309 material system achieved a weight savings of 46% of the equivalent diameter steel sphere. In addition, the design met the through thickness (primary strain/stress or membrane) conservative maximum allowable strain limit of -0.004200 mm/mm or maximum stress limit -283 MPa at design collapse pressure. Localized high strains in the vicinity of the titanium joint of -0.005750 mm/mm and a corresponding maximum localized stress of -386 MPa are predicted at collapse. The sphere will be fabricate using the fiber placement method to achieve a quasi-isotropic layup and an out-of-autoclave cure, and will be hydrostatically tested to collapse. Determination of the predicted failure pressure and failure mode will be made after the as-fabricated dimensions and as fabricated material properties are obtained. This assessment will be documented as part of the experimental report on the collapse test of the sphere. Upon completion and evaluation of the design and failure predictions of the sphere, a bispherical model composed of two graphite thermoset spheres joined at the reinforcing ring will be fabricated and tested. This model will be cycled to simulate service life prior to

collapse pressure tests.

5.0 TABLES

Table 1 - Preliminary Design of 1.2 Meter Diameter Sphere 1.91 cm Thick

Composite Material Fiber/Resin	NORMALIZED FACTOR-OF-SAFETY					
	BOSOR BUCKLING *		FIRST PLY FAILURE Ring & Cap		Maximum Strain (mm/mm)	Classical Buckling Perfect Sphere * (Eq. 3)
	Perfect Sphere	Ring with Cap	Tsai-Wu	Max. Stress		
AS4/3501	1.91	1.50	2.60	1.47	-0.00485	1.98
S-glass/Epoxy	0.82	0.64	0.82	0.78	-0.00601	0.84

* Includes 0.50 Knockdown Factor

Table 2 - Assumed AS4/3501-6 & AS4/309 Laminate Properties For Sphere Analysis With [0/45/-45/90]ns Layup

PROPERTY (1 = Radial 2 = Meridional 3 = Hoop)	AS4/3501-6		AS4/309
	ISOTROPIC (GPa)	TRANSVERSELY ISOTROPIC (GPa)	TRANSVERSELY ISOTROPIC (GPa)
E1	46.52	12.54	14.48
E2 = E3	46.52	46.52	42.26
NU23 = NU32	0.33	0.297	0.317
NU21 = NU31	0.33	0.375	0.367
G23	17.93	17.93	16.06
G12 = G13	17.93	3.00	4.27

Table 3 - Summary of Axisymmetric Solid F.E.M. Analyses of Sphere

Model Description	Analysis Code	Material	Properties	Maximum Strain (mm/mm) (Maximum Stress (MPa))		
				Radial	Meridional	Hoop
Initial, Fully Bonded Joint, Coarse Mesh, 1.91 cm Thick Sphere	FESOL	AS4/3501-6	Isotropic		{-286.1}	{-296.5}
				-0.00721 {-421.4}	-0.00398 {-262.4}	-0.00391 {-260.5}
ABAQUS	Transversely Isotropic		+0.00474 -0.00289	-0.00743	-0.00397	
			+0.00408 -0.00058	-0.00635	-0.00395	
			-0.01500	-0.00483	-0.00394	
			+0.00440	-0.00576	-0.00510	
Reduced Ring, Gap/Interface Fine, 1.651 cm Thick	AS4/309	+0.00209	-0.00644	-0.00537		
		+0.00438	-0.00575	-0.00470		
Reduced Ring, Gap/Interface Fine, 1.85 cm Thick						

6.0 FIGURES

Figure 1 - 1.22 Meter Diameter Bisphere with Joint

Figure 2 - Initial Trapped Mechanical Joint Concept

Figure 3 - Initial Axisymmetric Finite Element Model

Figure 4 - Crimping of Initial Sphere Model

Figure 5 - Final AS4/309 Sphere And Joint Model

Figure 6 - Meridional Strain Plot Final AS4/309 Model

7.0 REFERENCES

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8.0 NOMENCLATURE

b	= Width of Titanium Ring	p	= Hydrostatic Pressure
h	= $h_a = t_s$ = Thickness of Sphere	k	= Knockdown Factor
r_2	= Outside Radius of Titanium Ring	r_1	= Inside Radius of Titanium Ring
D	= Inside Diameter of Sphere	E_r	= Modulus of Elasticity of Ring
E_s	= Modulus of Elasticity of Sphere	E_t	= Tangent Modulus of Sphere
E_{sec}	= Secant Modulus of Sphere	L_c	= Critical Arc Length
P_{cr}	= Classical Elastic Critical Buckling Pressure		
P'_{cr}	= Modified Elastic Critical Buckling Pressure		
P_{exp}	= Elastic Critical Buckling Pressure Due to Out-of-Roundness		
P'_E	= Critical Buckling Pressure Above Proportional Limit		
P''_E	= P'_E With Fabrication Effects		
P_y	= Inelastic Yield Pressure		
R	= Mean Radius of Sphere		

- R_1 = Local Radius to Midsurface of Shell Over Critical Arc Length
 R_{10} = Local Radius to Outside Surface of Shell Over Critical Arc Length
 R_s = Inside Radius of Sphere
 α = Angle Defining Location of Shell Intersection
 δ_2 = Deflection of Titanium Ring
 ν_s = Poisson's Ratio for Sphere
 ν_r = Poisson's Ratio for Ring
 σ_{avg} = Average Stress in Sphere Above Proportional Limit
 σ_y = Yield Stress
 Δ = Deviation From Sphericity

9.0 BIOGRAPHY

Jeffrey C. Hall, Deputy Program Manager, General Dynamics/Electric Boat Division. Dr. Hall received his Ph.D. in Civil Engineering from Lehigh University in 1981. He began working at Electric Boat in 1981 developing and enhancing various nonlinear finite element programs. Starting in 1984 Dr. Hall developed the finite element structural optimization program FESOP, and in 1985 he began work on the Electric Boat Composite Design Software Network. He has published over 20 technical papers or reports on optimization or composites, and since 1989 has worked on the DARPA ASTP Composites Technology Development, Thick Composites Demonstration Program.

James J. Kelly is currently the Program Area Manager for Materials in the DARPA Advanced Submarine Technology Program. Mr. Kelly has been the Technical Area Manager for Materials in the Office of Naval Technology since 1980. He has served as a Congressional Science Fellow in 1986-1987 on both Congressman Don Ritter's staff and on the House Science and Technology Committee. Mr. Kelly has been a Materials Engineer for over 20 years. Mr. Kelly received a B. S. in Chemistry from Queens College and M. S. from Polytechnic University of New York in Management Science and Engineering. He has completed a number of graduate courses in materials engineering.

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